

Feature

Historical Weather Data Revisited The Erwin Knipping Project of the German Society for Natural and Ethnological Studies of East Asia

August Wierling and Valeria Jana Schwanitz,
Western Norway University of Applied Sciences

May 18, 2026

Abstract

The Erwin Knipping Project, run by the German Society for Natural and Ethnological Studies of East Asia (OAG), focuses on digitizing and analyzing handwritten weather records collected by Erwin Knipping (1844–1922). Knipping was a pioneer of early meteorology in Japan. From 1872 to 1878, he systematically documented meteorological observations that were later published in the Society's *Mitt(h)eilungen*.

Following the rediscovery of these largely overlooked climate data in the Society's archives, the project was initiated in 2024 by OAG members¹. With the help of students enrolled in a university-level methods course, the research team processed, scrutinized, and digitized the material. The resulting data set is now accessible to the scientific community and the public (publication for submission to a peer-reviewed data journal is underway).

This feature is an English translation of a three-part series on the project that was originally published in the OAG Newsletter. The first part of the series situates Knipping and his work within its historical context. The second explores the contemporary relevance of the data, including insights into climate change in Tokyo and future projections. The third demonstrates how modern data science techniques can unlock the value of historical meteorological records. This project contributes to international efforts to make pre-digital climate data usable for interdisciplinary research. The three parts of the original publication in German are available online, © OAG Tokyo ISSN 1343-408X:

I Knipping and the Japanese Climate, ► [Notizen 2601, 01/2026](#),

II Knipping's Data and Climate Change in Tokyo, ► [Notizen 2603, 03/2026](#),

III How digitized Data carries Knowledge through Time, ► [Notizen 202605, 05/2026](#).

¹Refer to the end of the publication for acknowledgments and author biographies.

Introduction

The Erwin Knipping Project of the German Society for Natural and Ethnological Studies of East Asia (OAG) in Tokyo is dedicated to the handwritten weather records of Erwin Knipping (1844–1922). Knipping, a member of the OAG and a pioneer of early meteorology in Japan, documented the weather between 1872 and 1878. Founded in 1873 by German merchants, scientists, and diplomats, the OAG conducts research on East Asia, particularly Japan, and shares its knowledge through lectures, publications, and cultural events. The Society’s publishing activities began in 1873, and its library comprises over 6,500 works in German and English. The OAG published Knipping’s weather data in its former *Mitteilungen*, now known as the OAG *Notizen* newsletter (►<https://oag.jp/books-cat/oag-notizen/>), in which this three-part series was originally published in German. Published ten times a year, the newsletter contains a feature article, reviews, editorials, association news, and announcements of upcoming events. Editor: Dr. Maike Roeder, © OAG Tokyo ISSN 1343-408X.

The project gained momentum in 2024 when Maike Roeder drew attention to Knipping’s previously overlooked climate data during an OAG study trip. The data had been lying dormant in the archives. “Couldn’t we do something with this?” she asked. As climate researchers passionate about historical research and data analysis, we were immediately enthusiastic. A year later, we began analyzing the records. Our Norwegian students supported us as part of the seven-week course on scientific methods. The result is a publication that makes the dataset digitally accessible to both the scientific community and the general public. Part I of the publication introduces Erwin Knipping. Over the years, he observed the weather in Japan using the instruments available at the time and meticulously documented methods and units, as well as measurement inaccuracies. Part II examines the current use of historical weather data, the impact of climate change on Tokyo, and projections through the year 2100. Part III demonstrates how modern data science can make historical datasets like Knipping’s accessible to humans and algorithms alike.

Part I: Knipping and the Japanese Climate

Erwin Knipping gazed out into the darkness around 9 p.m. on October 31, 1873, as he did every evening. But this time he saw something: the night sky over Tokyo was illuminated by the Northern Lights. He noted: “*Nl. Nm. 9u. Corona not visible, altitude 18°, arc 80°, 1 ½ to 2° wide, sharply defined on both sides, greenish white.*” (Knipping 1876: Observations October 1873). It was the 426th day of his weather records, taken several times a day; 2,619 daily notes were yet to follow. A few years later, the Japanese Meteorological Agency routinely continued the measurements, initially as the Imperial Weather Observatory, in which Knipping played a major role.

Erwin Knipping lived from 1844 to 1922, spending 20 of those years in Tokyo. He was a very hardworking man; meticulous as a sailor, diligent as a teacher of German and mathematics, busy and dedicated as a meteorologist (initially part-time, later in leadership roles in both Japan and Germany) - and prolific as a writer, authoring no fewer than 40 OAG articles. He was elected vice-chairman of the OAG in 1886, where he gave lectures. For example, on January 26, 1887, he spoke on “Typhoon Trajectories in Japan.” Anyone who wishes to get a sense of his diligence and conscientiousness can browse through the very first issue of the *OAG-Mitt(h)eilungen* (►<https://oag.jp/books/band-i-1873-1876-heft-1/>). The appendix contains the first of his detailed weather records (Knipping, 1876). Also highly recommended are articles on the sayings of Japanese farmers and one on the astonishingly accurate measurement of Mount Fuji by applying barometric altitude formulas during his ascent (Knipping, 1873b). No wonder that by the end of his life, Knipping had received several honors, including the Imperial Japanese Order of the Rising Sun, 1st Class; the Japanese Order of the Sacred Treasure, 3rd Class; and the German Order of the Crown of the Prussian Monarchy.

Knipping demonstrates his dedication regarding the so-called “Mannheim Hour” by comparing his own habits with those of his English colleagues:

Their hours were 9:30 a.m., 3:30 p.m., and 9:30 p.m.; my hours - 6:00 a.m., 2:00 p.m., and 10:00 p.m. - were less convenient but better suited to the task, and a uniform schedule was a necessity. A few observers who had become accustomed to the convenient English hours had left the service in 1872. To me, the administrative efficiency of the office was by far more important than my own or anyone else's convenience; that is why the service was the same on Sundays and holidays as on weekdays. Koch and Puster: p. 108)

And elsewhere he mentions:

Later, I heard through the grapevine that my Japanese superiors asked themselves how it was possible that I had been able to perform my daily duties without interruption for several years in a row and without falling ill. The only explanation that seemed to occur to them was that my copious consumption of meat had likely saved me from collapse. It is interesting in this context that my suggestion that the assistants each take turns providing the weather service for one week, daily at 6 a.m., 2 p.m., and 10 p.m., was rejected on the grounds that the Japanese could not endure it. So what I carried out for 150 consecutive weeks, the director could not expect the assistants to do for a single week. I had the best of intentions: to drill the weather patterns into people's minds. This makes it easier to predict the weather outlook. What's more, the assistants, like me, lived close to the observatory. (Koch and Puster: p. 119f.)

It is interesting to note in this context that the Japanese Meteorological Agency introduced weather measurements at three-hour intervals just a few years later.

An obituary in *Hansa –International Maritime Journal*, a magazine for nautical professions, perfectly summarizes Knipping's busy life and is therefore reproduced here in full (Hansa 1922):

At nearly 79 years of age, he died in Kiel on November 22 of this year. His name, closely associated with research on East Asian typhoons, is well known to older mariners. Knipping was born in Cleve in 1844; after passing his high school exams in 1862, he went to sea, sailing on German and Dutch vessels, and passed his exam as a "third mate" in Amsterdam at the end of November 1864. His former teacher, van Stee, who had noticed the young man's extraordinary talent, tried to recruit him as assistant and successor. The most prominent traits of his character - thoroughness and modesty - were already guiding the young Knipping, and despite the tempting prospects this offer held for the twenty-year-old deckhand, he did not dare to take on a position of such responsibilities without first acquiring the most thorough practical knowledge. The following years found him serving as second and first officer on steamships in East Asia. In May 1871, he remained ashore in Japan and worked as a teacher at the German secondary school in Tokyo until 1876. From 1876 to 1881, he was a member of the examination commission established in Tokyo for foreign captains and helmsmen of the Japanese merchant marine. He used his leave for extensive travels, resulting in six excellent route maps of Japan. His primary studies, however, were already focused on the field of earthquake research, which he pursued together with his friend Dr. Wagener, and on meteorology. The extensive observations he made and published drew the attention of the Japanese government, which commissioned him to organize the Japanese weather service. In 1887, he founded the telegraphic weather service in Japan, which he headed until 1891. In 1892, he moved his base of operations to Hamburg, where he worked at the German Hydrographic Office (Deutsche Seewarte) until 1909. For many years, he served as editor of the Annals of Hydrography and published a large number of valuable works on climatology, meteorology, and nautical astronomy. His nautical tables (Seetafeln) were also published in 1903. The "Hansa" owed him many valuable contributions that year. At the age of 66, he set out once more, spending a few years in Berkeley, California, then in Tientsin, until his wandering life finally brought him back to his starting point and he settled in Cleve. With him has died a seafarer who made many friends in all circles and of whom all Germans can be proud, because he knew how to earn respect and esteem for German skill, German thoroughness, and the German spirit at home and abroad. J. Krauss (Lübeck).

Meteorological instruments around 1870

Erwin Knipping himself writes that his interest in weather observation began as early as his school days. His mathematics teacher, Dr. Felten, “*was, on the side, a meteorological observer for the Prussian Statistical Office in Berlin, under Engel²,*” and thus “*one of the reasons that initially led me to meteorological observations in Tokyo and, in a sense, prepared me for my most important position in Japan.*” (Koch and Puster: p. 20). It was also Dr. Felten who, “*in 1872, when I was living in Tokyo, procured good meteorological instruments from Berlin, which my fiancée brought to me on her journey to Japan*” (ibid.).

Knipping published details of his equipment in the *OAG-Mitt(h)eilungen* in a particularly prominent place. In the very first issue of *the Mitt(h)eilungen*, immediately following the bylaws of the society founded in 1873, a list of instruments appears under the title “Meteorological Observations Recorded at the Station in Yedo, Japan”:

“1. Greiner No. 426 mercury barometer, Berlin, with a sliding scale, readable to 0.05 mm, with a thermometer on the scale and one inside the housing.”
(Knipping 1873a)

A mercury barometer works by utilizing the fact that the height of a liquid column inside a tube changes depending on atmospheric pressure, with the tube fed by a mercury bath. This method of measurement was the standard procedure before the widespread adoption of aneroid barometers, which measure atmospheric pressure based on the change in volume of an evacuated metal capsule. A mercury-thermometer barometer, in particular, is a mercury barometer with an integrated thermometer. It is needed to correct for the influence of temperature on the air pressure measurements, since the height of the mercury column depends both on fluctuating air pressure and on the thermal expansion of the mercury. Furthermore, the brass of the measuring scale expands at higher temperatures. This effect must be taken into account for precise measurements.

Knipping reports that he placed the barometer in an unheated room on the north side of the house, in accordance with the recommendations for scientific work at the time. He emphasizes this right in the first sentence: “*The forms and instructions in use at meteorological stations in the Prussian State serve as the basis [for the measurement procedure].*”

The sentence seems unremarkable, but it was central to our project with the students in order to verify and evaluate the accuracy of the data (more on this in Feature II). At that time, the so-called Prussian Instructions (*Instructions* 1858) set the scientific standard. They describe in detail how meteorological instruments should be installed, read, and maintained to avoid distorted measurements, especially since there was no uniformly organized weather measurement system in the mid-19th century. For the most part, it was laypeople who recorded daily weather data, transferred it to monthly forms, and then

²Ernst Engel (1821–1896; statistician and social economist).

sent it to national institutions for further evaluation and storage. Knipping sent his data to the “Royal Statistical Bureau in Berlin. Imperial Meteorological Service”(Instructions 1858: p. 23).

Since the observations were often conducted on a part-time basis - as was also the case with Knipping during the first years of his stay in Japan - hourly readings of the instruments could not always be guaranteed. The instructions therefore stipulated at least three readings per day. As already mentioned, Knipping deviated from this requirement and took measurements daily at the so-called “Mannheim hours”(7 a.m., 2 p.m., and 9 p.m.), likely also to better align the measurements with the daily rhythm of life. The term “Mannheim hour”derives from the practice of the Palatine Meteorological Society (Societas Meteorologica Palatina) and its secretary and director Johann Jakob Hemmer (1733–1790), which was at the time a leading institution for weather measurement in the German-speaking world.

In addition to the barometer, Knipping also had a psychrometer (two combined thermometers for measuring temperature and humidity). The so-called “dry thermometer” was a regular “*Greiner standard thermometer graduated in 5-degree Celsius increments.*” The second, identically constructed “wet thermometer,”however, was wrapped in a damp cloth at the lower end (e.g., in a cotton fabric moistened with water). This takes advantage of the fact that more water evaporates at lower humidity, and the energy of evaporation is drawn from the surrounding environment. The temperature indicated by the “wet-bulb thermometer”is thus lower than that of the dry-bulb thermometer, and the temperature difference is a direct and also very accurate measure of humidity. Psychrometers were the standard at many meteorological stations before the introduction of electrical solutions.

Knipping’s equipment was rounded out by a minimum and maximum thermometer, a thermometer for measuring well water temperature (“*by Callaghan, London*”), a Japanese-style rain gauge (“*manufactured in Yedo, the opening 1’Paris: the glass cylinder for measuring is graduated from 5 to 5 cubic centimeters; holds 500 cubic centimeters; the height is approximately 15 feet above sea level*”) and certainly, though not further described, a device for measuring wind direction. The aforementioned Prussian instructions provided for a wind vane for this purpose, “*whose eight cardinal directions must be correctly oriented and which is to be made at the observation site itself, if no reliable one is available there ...*”(Instructions 1858: p. 10).

Many of the measuring instruments described here were manufactured at that time by leading manufacturers. For example, the firm J. G. Greiner Jr. in Berlin was known for its precise instruments and the quality of its associated glassblowing craftsmanship. Rudolf Fuess took over the struggling firm in 1877, which also sold thermometers, barometers, and anemometers. Even today, equipment from this company can be found in many meteorological institutions.

Knipping thus possessed state-of-the-art instruments suitable for high-quality measure-

ments. He was all the more contrite after several years of measurements when measurement errors were discovered:

From the November 1880 issue of the Journal of the Austrian Meteorological Society, page 438, I see to my great regret that you did not receive a short article from the 17th issue of the German Society for the Natural History and Ethnology of East Asia [...]. I still cannot explain today how my otherwise excellent standard barometer, Greiner 426 (a Heber, read to 0.05 mm, with two microscopes), arrived at an index correction of -1.13 mm. The lower microscope can be shifted slightly on the movable scale, but I have never made any adjustments to it. Furthermore, the instrument was handled with the utmost care during the journey here and in Tokyo, so that the above index correction applies without exception to the entire series from 1872 to 1878. (Knipping 1881)

It is thanks to Knipping's thoroughness and self-correction that we were able to verify the data and compare it with the accuracy expected today.

The weather records

Knipping documents his “*observations in the courtyard of the Kaisegakko [sic!], teacher's residence No. 3 ... , at 35° 41' north latitude and approximately 139° 47' east longitude from Greenwich.*” (today: 1-chōme-12 Nihonbashi Ningyōchō, Chūō-ku, Tokyo 103-0013, Japan). An impression is given by Figure 1 of how the location of his weather station may have looked like, with inspiration drawn from a historical photograph of this old neighbourhood in Tokyo. Note that the starting point of the famous Tōkaidō trade route at the Nihonbashi Bridge is about 300 meters away.

Erwin Knipping's weather records contain a wealth of information. Figure 2 shows a snippet of the table for July 1873. The large number of columns is immediately apparent, as Knipping recorded not only direct measurements but also derived values, such as calculated humidity. Each row corresponds to a day, with the respective date listed on the left in the second column. The count was continuous, starting on January 1 and disregarding the change of month. In the 19th century, it was also customary to record the 5-day average (along with the arithmetic mean), since weeks fall on different dates in different years and comparability between years would otherwise be compromised. Today, these averages are no longer needed due to the greater availability of data. This results in a total of 73 5-day periods. The lowercase letter in the first column helps maintain an overview. Knipping consistently calculates the averages for almost all observed variables, with the exception of wind direction. This practice was already abandoned in Japan during Knipping's time. At the end of the data sheet, monthly totals and averages are also provided.

Figure 1: Knipping in front of the school in Tokyo (Kaisei Gakkō), where he conducted his weather observations from 1872 to 1878. Own illustration, inspired by a historical photograph.

TÄGLICHE BEOBSACHTUNG

		BAROMETRER PAR ZOLL UND LINIEN.												FETHTHERMOMETER (THERMOMETER 2 R.)						DUNSTSPANNUNG PAR LIN.				THERMOMETROGRAPH. R.				RELATIVE FEUCHTIGKEIT PROCENT.				Mittlere Werte des Tages (Therm. Bar.)		7h
		7h Morg.			9h Ab.			11h Ab.			Tägliche Mittel der 3 Beob.			7h Morg.		9h Ab.		Tägliche Mittel		Min.		Max.		Tägliche Mittel		7h Morg.		9h Ab.		Tägliche Mittel		7h		
		Therm. R. am Bar.			Therm. R. am Bar.			Therm. R. am Bar.			Therm. R. am Bar.			Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.		Trocken.				
30	Juli	28.57	21.1	28.217	23.8	28.338	22.5	28.044	28.154	28.071	21.0	13.9	28.0	20.5	21.6	18.9	9.95	9.30	9.11	9.45	10.4	25.3	22.85	65.4	60.6	77.8	75.9	22.57	S W					
31	Aug	28.37	20.3	28.308	22.5	28.332	22.7	28.171	28.145	28.167	28.161	18.9	18.9	20.5	21.6	18.9	9.04	10.18	10.30	9.54	10.3	23.9	21.60	67.7	61.3	86.1	85.03	21.50	S O					
1	Aug	28.356	20.4	28.301	22.4	28.336	22.9	28.185	28.132	28.170	28.162	19.4	19.2	20.4	21.8	18.9	9.72	9.41	10.12	9.75	10.6	24.6	21.60	68.0	64.2	84.6	82.27	21.50	S O					
2	Aug	28.359	19.8	28.302	22.1	28.350	22.6	28.207	28.162	28.188	28.186	21.1	20.2	24.6	21.2	21.0	10.85	10.82	9.81	9.56	10.6	24.8	22.70	91.2	70.4	85.4	81.57	21.28	S W					
3	Aug	28.359	19.8	28.377	23.0	28.350	22.6	28.254	28.210	28.185	28.216	17.9	17.7	24.3	20.2	21.2	8.68	9.50	9.98	9.04	17.9	24.3	21.10	97.9	66.4	78.5	80.93	21.15	W					
Summe.		16.15	108.4	15.89	116.8	16.66	118.1	8.61	6.94	8.94	7.96	9.3	9.6	7.121	10.2	10.7	4.774	48.71	47.77	48.07	95.9	122.9	109.85	464.2	342.9	410.4	405.83	108.85						
Mittel.		28.323	20.69	28.308	22.36	28.331	22.62	28.178	28.139	28.167	28.159	18.86	18.86	20.26	21.48	18.64	9.55	9.74	9.55	9.61	10.16	24.58	21.87	92.84	68.48	82.08	81.17	21.77	6 S					
4	Aug	28.314	20.6	28.308	22.4	28.330	22.1	28.164	28.139	28.189	28.164	18.8	18.7	24.4	19.9	21.0	9.07	9.83	9.57	9.52	10.6	24.6	21.70	88.7	61.5	76.3	75.57	21.55	N O					
5	Aug	28.341	20.7	28.259	22.9	28.323	21.0	28.198	28.193	28.170	28.169	18.7	18.2	23.6	18.6	20.0	17.0	8.69	7.72	7.50	7.87	18.6	23.8	21.20	97.0	67.0	70.7	70.67	20.83	S O				
6	Aug	28.346	19.5	28.323	22.2	28.343	21.6	28.202	28.162	28.186	28.188	18.6	16.1	23.4	17.8	20.7	6.92	6.97	6.88	7.52	17.6	23.4	20.20	73.9	62.2	78.3	86.47	20.85	S O					
7	Aug	28.348	18.6	28.328	22.4	28.326	21.8	28.211	28.167	28.177	28.185	16.8	16.5	23.7	19.4	21.0	7.58	8.62	8.78	8.89	16.6	23.6	20.30	96.7	62.6	75.4	79.20	20.63	W					
8	Aug	28.322	20.2	28.279	23.1	28.237	22.1	28.177	28.110	28.127	28.121	15.4	18.2	24.3	15.9	21.0	8.69	8.86	8.98	8.83	18.3	24.3	21.30	87.6	62.2	78.5	76.10	21.33	S W					
Summe.		16.73	99.1	15.05	115.3	15.89	108.6	5.47	6.71	7.99	8.05	9.4	8.7	7.119	4.95	10.8	41.15	40.90	42.26	41.43	90.1	119.9	105.00	431.4	295.4	382.9	369.91	104.39						
Mittel.		28.325	19.82	28.301	22.06	28.318	21.79	28.189	28.134	28.160	28.161	18.86	17.54	23.88	19.12	20.78	8.23	8.18	8.45	8.59	18.02	23.58	21.60	86.28	69.08	76.58	73.98	21.08	4 S					
9	Aug	28.306	19.6	28.189	23.8	28.163	22.7	28.058	27.1136	27.1143	28.001	18.2	17.9	24.7	20.7	21.2	8.77	9.75	9.89	9.47	17.1	24.7	20.80	96.8	66.2	87.5	83.60	21.33	N W					
10	Aug	28.029	19.4	27.1107	23.8	27.109	22.7	27.1120	27.954	27.801	27.872	18.4	17.4	19.9	24.7	20.7	8.09	9.19	8.61	8.51	17.5	25.1	21.20	74.4	62.3	75.4	70.98	22.23	N					
11	Aug	27.1154	21.8	27.1115	24.2	27.1060	22.7	27.927	27.942	27.897	27.945	21.4	18.9	24.4	19.6	22.0	8.77	8.53	8.47	8.49	21.0	24.4	22.70	76.0	69.4	70.3	68.27	22.45	S W					
12	Aug	27.071	22.0	27.1016	25.0	27.1052	23.4	27.819	27.838	27.856	27.848	22.2	18.9	25.9	21.8	22.7	9.27	10.59	9.57	9.94	21.1	25.2	23.55	79.3	66.0	75.8	73.27	23.38	S W					
13	Aug	27.1158	20.6	28.059	23.7	28.100	22.8	27.1026	27.1089	27.1136	27.1078	19.0	18.5	24.8	21.0	21.8	9.13	10.15	9.88	9.72	15.0	24.4	21.70	94.8	70.9	88.1	82.98	21.73	O					
Summe.		65.61	108.6	69.25	130.9	66.94	114.9	62.01	50.59	48.74	50.44	99.6	92.6	125.1	108.6	109.9	44.83	48.15	46.52	46.33	95.7	135.5	110.60	481.1	319.7	387.1	379.30	111.14	1 N					
Mittel.		27.1150	20.72	27.1185	24.18	27.1189	22.86	27.1040	27.1012	27.975	27.975	20.09	19.22	25.02	21.98	21.98	9.67	9.63	9.80	9.27	19.14	25.10	22.12	86.22	68.84	78.27	75.86	22.28	2 S					
14	Aug	28.194	21.6	28.137	24.8	28.195	23.0	27.1166	27.1159	28.030	27.1185	21.7	19.2	25.7	20.6	21.6	8.97	9.17	9.29	9.19	20.7	25.0	23.20	76.1	68.2	78.7	71.00	22.65	S W					
15	Aug	28.208	21.8	28.244	24.5	28.238	22.7	28.109	28.068	28.108	28.098	18.7	18.6	19.1	20.6	19.8	8.84	9.91	8.71	8.75	18.8	24.2	23.25	74.4	62.3	75.4	70.98	22.23	N					
16	Aug	28.314	20.3	28.308	23.0	28.333	21.9	28.166	28.141	28.174	28.160	19.2	18.3	24.7	20.1	20.6	8.86	9.02	9.47	9.12	18.2	24.7	21.45	90.6	61.3	86.2	80.03	21.39	S W					
17	Aug	28.281	19.4	28.237	23.8	28.235	21.6	28.139	28.090	28.151	28.155	18.8	18.0	18.6	17.6	18.0	8.89	9.38	9.74	9.55	17.7	23.3	23.25	96.9	60.3	97.9	95.03	23.20	N O					
18	Aug	28.301	18.3	28.265	21.4	28.166	21.8	28.146	28.110	28.146	28.141	17.7	17.8	23.2	19.0	20.2	8.94	8.60	9.04	8.66	17.1	23.2	19.65	96.6	61.3	86.8	83.90	21.08	N O					
Summe.		12.88	101.6	11.92	114.4	13.92	108.4	5.46	3.64	6.03	5.04	98.7	91.9	116.2	97.8	101.9	43.84	44.61	44.88	44.45	94.4	118.7	106.60	433.6	342.4	423.0	399.66	104.64						
Mittel.		28.258	20.52	28.235	22.90	28.247	21.68	28.109	28.078	28.121	28.101	19.74	18.28	23.84	19.56	20.36	8.77	8.92	8.98	8.89	18.90	23.74	21.32	86.72	68.48	79.94	78.24	22.58	2 S					
19	Aug	28.281	18.8	28.233	22.7	28.272	21.7	28.148	28.059	28.114	28.109	17.6	17.8	23.2	19.6	20.9	8.57	8.91	8.60	8.59	17.4	23.4	20.40	96.7	67.8	77.3	80.60	20.55	S W					
20	Aug	28.295	20.7	28.277	23.6	28.330	21.9	28.144	28.105	28.171	28.140	20.8	18.6	24.9	19.8	21.2	8.64	9.91	8.71	8.75	18.8	24.2	21.20	94.8	64.4	75.6	73.10	21.78	S W					
21	Aug	28.330	21.4	28.319	23.5	28.405	22.2	28.174	28.149	28.243	28.189	21.1	19.0	24.3	20.1	21.3	8.56	9.24	8.89	9.63	20.8	24.2	23.52	79.4	64.6	70.3	78.27	22.00	S W					
22	Aug	28.335	20.3	28.405	22.7	28.403	21.5	28.276	28.249	28.246	28.254	19.8	18.4	23.4	20.2	20.6	8.57	9.51	9.03	9.17	18.0	23.4	21.20	86.6	71.5	85.1	80.60	21.10	N O					
23	Aug	28.322	20.3	28.343	22.5	28.323	21.0	28.241	28.182	28.170	28.198	19.4	18.6	22.6	19.9	20.0	8.10	9.43	8.87	9.19	19.4	24.2	21.00	91.7	74.9	84.6	83.73	20.45	N O					
Summe.		17.23	101.9	16.79	115.0	17.33	108.3	9.78	7.46	9.44	8.90	98.7	92.0	117.4	99.7	104.1	43.94	46.10	44.10	44.71	96.4	117.9	107.15	432.7	343.2	396.2	391.70	106.08						
Mittel.		28.345	20.56	28.316	23.00	28.347	21.66	28.196	28.149	28.189	28.178	19.74	18.40	23.84	19.54	20.82	8.79	9.22	8.82	8.94	19.28	23.58	21.43	86.64	68.54	79.94	78.24	22.58	2 S					
24	Aug	28.332	20.6	28.277	22.6	28.299	21.8	28.186	28.113	28.140	28.146	18.9	18.2	22.6	20.2	20.8	8.85	8.89	9.48	9.41	18.9	22.6	20.76	92.8	78.4	86.3	85.88	20.78	S W					
25	Aug	28.277	19.8	28.237	22.4	28.245	21.8	28.132	28.088	28.088	28.088	1																						

It is noticeable that the measured values for barometric pressure and temperature are not given in the units commonly used today (i.e., in hectopascals or degrees Celsius). As mentioned earlier, Knipping used a mercury barometer on which air pressure was readable in millimeters of mercury. However, he did not record the values in millimeters, but rather in the Parisian units of the time - par inch and lines - which originated in pre-revolutionary France. It was not until after the Revolution, in 1799, that a standard meter of 443.296 Parisian lines was established. Dashes are usually used to denote this unit: a single dash stands for a foot, a double dash for an inch, and a triple dash for the Parisian line itself.

This system of units, widely used at the time, has only survived in a few places. For example, wick widths for oil lamps or watch dials for prestigious Swiss brands are still measured in Parisian lines, and the typographic Didot point is exactly one-sixth of a Parisian line. It was not until 1875 that the International Meter Convention agreed on the units of measurement, the meter and the kilogram, that are common use today. Japan acceded to the convention in 1876. In practice, however, Knipping still uses Parisian lines for all length-related measurements, such as when specifying precipitation amounts.

Knipping expresses temperatures in degrees Réaumur (°R). This temperature scale was introduced in 1730 by the French naturalist René-Antoine Ferchault de Réaumur (1683–1757). However, it was Jean André Deluc (1727–1817) who provided its scientific foundation. A Réaumur thermometer is based on the expansion of alcohol. It uses the freezing point of water as the sole reference point for calibration and ends at approximately 80°R, the boiling point of alcohol. It was, however, impractical to read the temperature by counting backward from the maximum value. Deluc simplified this and also developed a mercury thermometer with two calibration points (zero at the freezing point of water, 80°R at the boiling point of water - today 100°C).

Although the Réaumur scale quickly became popular in German-speaking and Eastern European regions, there was still a great deal of confusion, and people joked about it, for example, in the *Oberhessischer Anzeiger* in 1882:

The Germans mostly use the thermometer devised by the Frenchman Réaumur, the French use the thermometer devised by the Swede Celsius, and the English and Americans use the thermometer devised by the German Fahrenheit; consequently, no nation uses the one devised by its own countryman.

It was only a new regulation that brought about standardization. The *General-Anzeiger* for Duisburg, Ruhrort, and the surrounding area commented on this in its February 5, 1901, edition:

Recently, a notice made the rounds in the newspapers stating that in the future, in all public institutions, businesses, etc., only the Celsius thermometer, which measures in hundredths, is to be used for measuring temperature.

This effectively declared war - at least for official use - on the Réaumur and Fahrenheit scales, both of which are still in use, the former particularly here in Germany and the latter especially in America, although there is little reason to fear that, for example, the Réaumur thermometer will now simply be cast aside as useless and worthless.

In the end we note that Germany continued to use °R well into the 1900s.³ Japan switched to °C in 1885 after a five-year dispute between the Ministry of the Interior (which was pro-British, i.e., in favor of the yard, pound, and Fahrenheit) and the Ministry of Industry and Agriculture.

While Knipping measured temperature and air pressure in physical units, he still expressed wind speed using a phenomenological scale. Wind force 2 on the 4-point scale, for example, meant that the wind “*sways trees slightly, occasionally hinders walking, and causes a more or less faint whistling sound outdoors.*” (Instructions from 1858) Knipping participated in the discussion to replace this rather crude scale. Later, the 12-point Beaufort scale was adopted, which had been used in maritime navigation since the mid-19th century. In some publications, Knipping already applied the modern unit of meters per second for wind speed; however, in his observations from 1872–1878 in Tokyo, he used only the four-point scale, which makes conversion to modern values quite difficult, as only a possible range of wind speeds can be specified. For wind directions, Knipping used an eight-point wind rose.

Knipping supplements his measurements with a so-called sky survey, observations of electrical phenomena, etc. For a sky survey, “*the observer must go to an open location if his residence has too restricted a horizon. The extent of cloud cover is, after some practice, easy to estimate if one determines it in 10-degree increments.*” (Instructions 1858: p. 12) A five, for example, means “*as many clouds as there is blue sky.*” Knipping recorded cloud shapes using Howard’s terminology. He distinguished between stratus clouds, cumulus clouds, cirrus clouds, and various mixed forms, as is still common today. Also of interest are the observations recorded under “General Remarks.” He notes earthquakes or thunderstorms on several occasions, but also, at times, “*rain gauge spout burst.*” Noteworthy are his observations regarding the eruption of the supervolcano Krakatoa:

As I was walking through the palace on August 26 or 27, 1883, the sun was already very high in the sky, and I noticed that one could look directly at the sun without any trouble, for it seemed to be covered by a thick veil. The phenomenon seemed inexplicable to me. An inquiry was also sent from the Office of the Court Marshal to the observatory, but we had no explanation.

³If you’d like, you can take a look at Thomas Mann’s **The Magic Mountain** to see how room temperatures are specified there; and in Switzerland and Italy, the old French unit °R is still used in cheese production, for example, in the making of Parmigiano Reggiano, or in the preparation of meringue mixtures.

The explanation only came when the telegraph brought news of the terrible eruption of Krakatoa in the Sunda Strait [...] So what veiled the sun in Tokyo were finely dispersed particles of dust and ash originating from Krakatoa. They were hurled up to 30 km in height. (Koch and Puster: p. 112f.)

For the year 1873, Knipping published his daily data in the *OAG-Mitt(h)eilungen*, but data for other years are missing. Since Knipping stated that he had sent this data to the Royal Prussian Meteorological Institute, it may still be found in the institute's archives. However, the premises and materials are currently inaccessible due to renovation work. Knipping did, however, include the monthly summaries of the data in several issues of the *Mitt(h)eilungen*. In his memoirs, he writes about the end of his weather records:

Since the Japanese government had established a well-equipped official observatory under English management a few years earlier (1875), I ceased my observations in 1878 and began studying typhoons as a substitute. (Koch and Puster, p. 81)

Part II: Knipping's Data and Climate Change in Tokyo

From Weather Records to Climate Research

The term "climate" refers to the weather conditions at a given location averaged over decades - usually 30 years. Depending on the area, ranging from a continent to a forest lake, we speak of macro and microclimates. The values are averaged over time and space. Erwin Knipping began his weather recordings in Tokyo: from 1872 to 1876 near his apartment on the grounds of the Kaisei School, and then until 1878 in Surugadai, not far from today's Imperial Palace. He measured temperature, humidity, air pressure, precipitation, wind speed and direction, air density, cloud cover, visibility, and more. This data allows for precise conclusions about the microclimate of his district at that time.

As mentioned in the first part of this feature, we owe to Knipping the compilation of weather data from all over Japan. Although Western visitors such as Philipp Franz von Siebold had observed the weather earlier, it was not until 1875 that the Japanese government began establishing its own meteorological service. Weather stations were set up throughout the country: by 1893, there were 10 first-class stations, 37 second-class stations, and over 340 third-class stations - classified according to technical equipment and staffing (Central Meteorological Observatory of Japan 1893). Daily temperature and precipitation measurements became standard, while air pressure recordings remained rare at first. Hokkaidō was a pioneer: the first Japanese station was established there as early as 1872, and two decades later there were 62. This data helped develop agriculture in the island's harsh climate.

Knipping played a key role in establishing the Japanese meteorological service. He introduced telegraphic transmission protocols and standardized the data. To this end, he created a concise, unambiguous transmission standard—a relief for the telegraph operators. Only the overall view of the values revealed how temperatures, as well as high- and low-pressure areas, were distributed on a large scale.

In 1883, Knipping drew Japan's first weather map (see image) - a milestone. Constructing lines of equal pressure, i.e., isobars, from individual measurement points required skill and ingenuity. Calculating and extrapolating climatic conditions for parts of the country or all of Japan by hand and with the help of tables was extremely challenging.

The timing of the measurements remained critical. Local time references, such as those based on the sun's position, led to discrepancies: in Fukuoka, the sun reaches its zenith 41 minutes later than in Sendai. Knipping therefore proposed a uniform time zone for Japan.

Today, the Japanese Meteorological Agency (JMA), the Japanese Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), and the National Institute for Environmental Studies (NIES) take the lead in weather recording and climate modeling. Manual measurements have given way to digital recording. In addition to stationary measuring stations, buoys, ships, and satellites provide data that is supplemented by computer-based models. Everything is standardized worldwide under the *World Meteorological Organization*. Long-term projects record over 50 climate variables. Tokyo is designated by the code 47662 in the global data system.

Finally, a few details about satellites and automatic weather stations. *Himawari* (sunflower) refers to a series of Japanese geostationary satellites that monitor the weather and forecast typhoons. Just as a sunflower always follows the sun, the satellite keeps a steadfast eye on Japan, hence the name. The first satellite was launched in 1977 and was decommissioned in 1989. Since 2022, *Himawari 9* has used its 16-channel camera to provide images in the visible and infrared spectrum, from which surface temperatures can be calculated. In addition, the Japanese Meteorological Agency operates AMeDAS, the *Automated Meteorological Data Acquisition System*, with 840 automated weather stations. They measure wind direction, wind speed, temperature, humidity, and precipitation. Additionally, 1,300 stations equipped with rain gauges, 1,100 of which are unmanned, collect data every 10 minutes at intervals of 17 kilometers. This information is transmitted via dedicated telephone lines to the headquarters of the Japanese Meteorological Agency. The system was launched on November 1, 1974, and was modernized on March 26, 2008; since then, the measurement frequency has been 10 seconds instead of 10 minutes. Since 2021, instruments have been updated in many locations, for example with ultrasound-based wind speed sensors. All data is also being digitized and prepared for communication with artificial intelligence.

Climate Change Research –Tokyo Is a Global Hotspot

What do we know about Japan’s climate and how it has changed over the past few centuries? Zaiki Masumi of Seikei University in Tokyo and her team have been reconstructing the climate since the Edo period (1603-1868) for the past twenty years. They analyze historical sources, including data from Knipping, and thus trace the progression of the average July temperature in Tokyo since 1721 step by step.

Figure 5 shows marked drops in temperature: around 1740, 1783, and 1883. These cold spells were likely triggered by volcanic eruptions, leading to crop failures and even the great drought of the Tenmei period (1781–1789). Comparing local and global climate data clarifies whether eruptions had only regional or global effects. For example, the cool summer of 1783 was likely a local phenomenon, caused by the eruption of Mount Asama in Nagano Prefecture. In contrast, the 1739 eruption of Mount Tarumae, amplified by an El Niño phase, had global consequences. 1740 was the coldest year in Europe in 600 years (Brönnimann et al. 2024). The figure also clearly shows the long-term rise in July temperatures during the 20th century. Since 2011, this trend has even accelerated, which is a clear sign of global warming.

According to *the 2024 World Climate Report* (World Meteorological Organization 2024), the global average temperature two years ago was 1.55 ± 0.13 degrees Celsius above the 1850–1900 average. The warming is affecting different regions to varying degrees. Around Japan, the average sea surface temperature is rising rapidly, that is, twice as fast as the global average. Tokyo is also warming at an above-average rate: over the past 100 years, temperatures have risen by about 3 degrees Celsius (see Fig. 3). The urban heat island effect is driving this increase: dark asphalt, glass facades, and concrete store heat and slow down nighttime cooling. The dense urban development additionally blocks fresh air currents.

The climate system is complex, and its consequences cannot be predicted with precision. For example, the impact of global warming on precipitation in Tokyo remains unclear, since two opposing effects are at play. In the city, relative humidity is decreasing, which suggests less rain. At the same time, an increase in condensation nuclei promotes the formation of water droplets. Condensation nuclei are tiny particles in the air, such as dust, salt, or pollen. They act as “starting points” where water vapor from the air can condense into tiny water droplets. Which force prevails and what other influences come into play remains to be seen. However, analyses by Higashino Makoto (Oita College of Technology) and Heinz Stefan (University of Minnesota) show that over the past 100 years, annual rainfall in Tokyo has decreased by about 14 percent (Higashino and Stefan 2020).

Japan runs the risk of losing its distinct seasons, as the *Japan Times* also highlighted in a headline: “Autumn Is the New Summer - Global Warming Threatens Japan’s Cultural Calendar”(Otake 2023). Ocean currents, monsoons, jet streams, and other climatic factors are shifting and forming new patterns.

Figure 4: The graph shows the average July temperature from 1721 to 2025. The solid line represents an 11-year average based on historical weather records. The dashed line represents the 11-year average of JMA data from 1875 to the present. Open circles mark individual measurements, while squares represent individual values from the reconstruction.

Figure 5: Average annual temperature from 1876 to 2025 (unfilled circles), published by the Japanese Meteorological Agency for the Tokyo observation station (WMO-ID 47662). The filled circles represent average annual temperatures, calculated from Knipping's daily measurements. The dashed curve is a regression line: a line of best fit that best matches the statistically fluctuating values. The regression covers the last 100 years. Its slope indicates a temperature increase of 3 degrees Celsius over the last 100 years (own calculation and presentation).

Climate data from measurements and models are supplemented worldwide and in Japan by systematic, phenomenological observations of climate change. For a change, let's not focus on cherry blossoms - though they are the prime example, since their onset and duration in Japan can be traced back to the 9th century thanks to diary entries (Christidis et al. 2022).

Instead, here are some examples of the ongoing northward spread of insects, such as the Great Mormon butterfly (*Papilio memnon*). Researchers compared the cold tolerance of its pupae across four populations, including one from a subtropical region and one from the northernmost part of Japan. The results suggest that the recent northward migration is due to warming. Conditions for the overwintering of the green stink bug (also known as the rice bug, Japanese: *Kamemushi*, *Nesara viridula*) in many regions of central Japan have also improved over the past 45 years (Tougou et al. 2009). This has likely facilitated its northward spread, a direct response to warming. Between 1910 and the early 1990s, the species expanded into higher latitudes: from Kyūshū (33° N) to central Honshū (36° N). This northward shift coincides with the expansion of areas where the annual average temperature exceeds 15 °C; the warming of the past 100 years is considered a key driver of this development.

The consequences extend beyond altered seasonal cues such as insect chirping. Wood-boring insects, for instance, are becoming an increasing problem: in recent years, damage caused by wood-boring species has occurred, particularly at the Sanbutsudō in the Rinnō-ji temple complex. Warmer zones can increase the abundance of insects such as the long-horned beetle (*P. cylindricum*). However, the life cycle of this rare Anobiidae species has not yet been fully studied (Brimblecombe and Hayashi 2018).

Global climate change is leading to more and more extreme weather events in Tokyo as well. The previous record for the highest November temperature, set in 1923, was surpassed by 0.2 degrees Celsius in 2023 and now stands at 27.5 degrees Celsius. On August 11, 2013, the minimum temperature did not drop below 30 degrees Celsius for the first time. This, too, demonstrates how rapidly the city's climate is changing.

New Perspectives in Climate Research: Long-term scenarios and data-driven simulation

By 2100, the Earth should warm by less than two degrees Celsius compared to pre-industrial times. This is what was agreed upon in the Paris Climate Agreement. The pre-industrial level is defined as the average of the years 1850–1900. Climate research is thus broadening its perspective: it does not stop at analyzing past data but ventures into long-term projections. These are not predictions, which are impossible, but scenario analyses, calculated using complex climate models. These interdisciplinary models depict the interactions between the atmosphere, oceans, land use, the economy, and energy and resource consumption. They consist of many coupled model components, thereby allowing the study of feedback loops. Their backbone consists of systems of mathematical

equations. They describe processes in nature (such as the production of greenhouse gases through the use of fossil fuels) and in human society (such as the demand for agricultural land or energy). To determine initial values and parameters, the models require extensive historical data; the more precise, the better. That is why it is extremely helpful to have access to many different datasets. This allows for testing and reduces uncertainties. This is also where the added value of Knipping’s data lies.

There is no single, all-encompassing global climate model; rather, there are several hundred. They differ in spatial resolution, thematic focus, time horizon, and simulation approach, whether optimization or simulation. The models compete against one another in standardized tests, which enables comparison and validation and complements the standard peer review process. These additional model evaluations are organized within the *Coupled Model Intercomparison Project* (CMIP) of the World Climate Research Programme (►<https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-overview/>).

The *Asia-Pacific Integrated Model* (AIM) family is a globally recognized computer model with planetary resolution. At the same time, it specializes in detailed climate scenarios for Asia and Japan (Hibino and Masui 2023). AIM provides reference scenarios for the reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). It also generates computational results for the Asian Ministerial Conference on the Environment, the UNEP *Global Environmental Outlook Program*, the *UN Global Modeling Forum*, and the *Asia-Pacific Network Program*. The research project to develop AIM began in 1990 at the National Institute for Environmental Studies (NIES) in collaboration with Professor Emeritus Matsuoka Yuzuru of Kyoto University. Just four years later, it was expanded into an international cooperation program to develop national models, involving leading research institutes in several Asian countries.

A key outcome of the global collaboration among climate modelers is the development of shared climate change scenarios for the period 2000–2100: the *Shared Socioeconomic Pathways* (SSPs). These scenarios describe possible future trajectories—depending on how socioeconomic development might unfold. Five consistent scenarios were developed through multi-year international research projects, which are:

- SSP1 Sustainability (Taking the Green Road),
- SSP2 Mid-Path (Middle of the Road),
- SSP3 Regional Rivalry (A Rocky Road),
- SSP4 Inequality (A Road Divided) and
- SSP5 Fossil-Fueled Development (Taking the Highway).

These were fed into multi-component models, and through repeated runs, the scenarios could be gradually quantified. AIM is one of the models that has developed data-driven

reference scenarios. The SSPs enable standardized studies of the potential impacts of climate change, and they assist in planning mitigation and adaptation measures.

A research team at the University of Tokyo used the SSP scenarios as a starting point to develop three possible future scenarios for the megacity of Tokyo (Kamei et al. 2016). The researchers sought to determine how the city could adapt to climate change, taking into account expected demographic and economic trends. The researchers identified three baseline scenarios:

- Tokyo Local Vitality Scenario, which prioritizes creativity and social capital,
- Tokyo Efficiency Scenario, transforming the city to operate more efficiently, and
- Business-As-Usual Scenario, which is used for comparison.

Such simulations reveal dead ends, highlight windows of opportunity, and facilitate discussions with stakeholders and policymakers, because they provide concrete visions and take into account various projections and trend analyses.

In Tokyo, for example, residents must prepare for significantly more days with temperatures exceeding 35 degrees Celsius in the future (Ishizaki et al. 2022). Experts expect that by the end of the century, the number of heat-related rescue operations will be about three times higher than today for people under 65. For those over 65, it could even be six times higher (Fujimoto and Nishiura 2022).

As it happens, Japanese scientists also use data from European satellites to project climate change. Recently, flood risks for Tokyo were calculated with the help of Copernicus. The results show that areas affected by flooding of 25 centimetres or more could increase by 25 per cent between 2016 and 2035, and by as much as 55 per cent by 2076–2095 (Amaguchi et al., 2024). Tokyo residents will probably have to plan ahead (or roll up their pants more often).

Part III: How digitized data carries knowledge through time - using Knipping’s historical data as an example

Tables as cultural achievements

Looking at the tables Knipping used to document his meteorological data, it quickly becomes clear that these are monthly entries (Fig. 6). The header lists months such as July, August, and September, and the rows are labeled as in row 10: “Die Zahl der Gewitter war / The number of thunderstorms was”. The meaning of the table’s cells is also easy to interpret. One intuitively understands why some elements are highlighted (through italics, boldface, and underlining) or why symbols are used, such as dots or quotation marks. Such a tabular structure can, without exaggeration, be described as

Humans sometimes use periods instead of quotation marks. Furthermore, periods separate decimal places. This leads to the next problem. Knipping used a period to indicate the decimal place, whereas in Germany today a comma is usually the norm. Japan, on the other hand, follows the Anglo-Saxon tradition. So what does a period mean? Such details must be understood by both humans and computers alike.

Digitizing historical records requires that humans and computers speak the same language. The French artist Barbara Bellier has vividly illustrated this in Figure 7. The first step is to understand what information Knipping intended to convey at the time. Specifically: What did he want to say? And how did readers of his era interpret it? Knowledge is always directed at a target audience whose background and mindset determine how the information is presented. Knipping primarily addressed meteorologists, as they were his main audience. Even back then, his contributions to the OAG-Mitteilungen newsletter garnered worldwide attention in professional journals, as evidenced by numerous citations and references. These readers had a specific way of reading and interpreting the data. But such contexts often change more drastically than we realize. Have you noticed that Knipping's table (Fig. 6) does not specify units for the monthly barometric pressure (row 1) or the monthly maximum temperature (row 5)? Anyone expecting hectopascals or degrees Celsius is mistaken. In fact, the units are Parisian lines and Réaumur (see also Part I of this feature).

Figure 7: This cartoon by French artist Barbara Bellier illustrates that humans and computers must speak the same language in order to analyze large amount of diverse data. The image rights belong to the authors.

Another aspect of the previous considerations regarding the target audience deserves attention. In the digital age, data should also be understandable and usable for a secondary readership. This not only serves transparency or the dissemination of knowledge but it also opens the door to broader user groups and new applications. That is the great advantage of digitization and automated data analysis, requiring new approaches in the philosophy of science. We are right in the middle of this development, but we are still far from our goal.

No documentation, no matter how good it may be, is error-free. Let's take another look at Figure 6. Under entry number 7, three lines are highlighted. They contain a typographical error. For the months of July, August, and September, there are three precipitation values listed: the total rainfall in cubic inches, as well as the respective proportions of rain and snow. Since snow in Tokyo was and is extremely unlikely in the summer (as confirmed by the line in the snow column), the first and second values should match. This is true for August and September, but in July the values differ. The table therefore contains a clear typographical error.

The most common source of error is entries based on calculations. Monthly averages were difficult to determine, as dividing by 31 days often led to errors without a calculator - whether through mental arithmetic or by consulting the reference tables commonly used at the time. Another example is found in line 9: "The average wind direction is calculated from this ...". Knipping's table does not reveal how the average was calculated from the eight wind frequencies of the various directions. Our research revealed that the so-called Lambert formula was applied. However, this formula is no longer relevant today. The decision to stop using it is the result of a long discussion among meteorologists. What is the point of an average wind direction anyway? Suppose the wind almost always blew from the northwest. Then the average should reflect that. Yet a northwesterly average can also result if the wind never came from the northwest, but instead blew equally often from the north and west. Because of this ambiguity, a wind rose visualization is used today, which represents wind speeds and frequencies along axes, thereby solving the problem.

The challenge in digitizing data lies in handling errors correctly and leveraging implicit knowledge to detect them as automatically as possible. Sometimes errors can be corrected by drawing conclusions from other information, such as by checking totals. But often that isn't possible. So which of the rainfall amounts is the correct one? Then the question remains as to what to report instead and what consequences the gap will have. The situation is similarly difficult with illegible digits: for example, 3, 6, and 8 are often hard to tell apart.

Figure 6 also highlights a linguistic issue: Knipping spoke of "rainfall total," but from today's perspective, he meant "precipitation total." Whether the terms are synonymous depends on the context and the linguistic usage of the time in question. In colloquial language, they may still mean the same thing, but scientifically, "precipitation" is the umbrella term for rain, snow, hail, and similar phenomena. Each era, however, follows its own linguistic and scientific standards. The digitization of data requires that changes in these standards be recognized and automatically accounted for.

In any case, it still remains uncertain whether we will then have all the information needed to fully reconstruct the state of knowledge among Knipping's readership at the time. So far, we have merely ensured that we interpret the table entries correctly, including how to handle omissions or misprints, and have developed confidence that the entries are

largely accurate and were carefully compiled. However, this by no means guarantees that Knipping’s data was collected correctly. One example of this is his own observation that the barometer was incorrectly calibrated for five years, leading to erroneous measurements (see Feature I). Such errors often only become apparent when compared with alternatives, such as other measurement series or simulation results.

In Knipping’s case, data from the Japanese Mining Bureau (永田町鑛山寮氣象觀測表) for the period 1872–1876 and, starting in 1875, data from the Imperial Meteorological Institute can be used for comparison. However, it is important to note that the measurements were not taken at exactly the same locations or times, as the weather stations were about three kilometers apart. This may sound like nitpicking, but it has consequences, for example in the case of typhoons. The measured rainfall can vary significantly between the two locations, depending on the path of the relatively narrow rain bands. Furthermore, in strong winds, less precipitation reaches the measuring device, which can lead to considerable discrepancies. It was therefore not surprising that the comparison of the datasets revealed significant differences, particularly during the typhoon season. The task, therefore, is to analyze these discrepancies and clarify their causes. Added to this are instrumental measurement errors, reading inaccuracies, and natural statistical fluctuations. The question is how large a discrepancy is permissible for the data to still be considered valid. The air pressure readings from the Mining Office, for example, deviate so significantly from the other two datasets that they should be viewed with skepticism.

From Human to Computer

As we have just discussed, the careful examination of historical data and its context constitutes the first step toward digitization. This cannot be done without the in-depth thinking of a human being. Computers still fail at this step, but algorithms can provide support, for example, in performing computational checks. How can the transition to the complete digitization of data and context be achieved so that computers can process the information for various target groups? How do we teach computers what humans think and have thought? How do we formulate an instruction that allows the computer to access the complex network of knowledge derived from observations, context, and background information at any time and incorporate it into its interpretation?

The answer can be illustrated with an example. Let’s take a detour into linguistics. We will examine how semantic methods help to interconnect knowledge. First, we will analyze how humans read a question, link knowledge, and find answers. Then we will compare this with a machine’s approach. The question we are examining is: what does a temperature difference of 5 degrees Celsius between noon and evening mean?

A person reads the letters, recognizes words, and understands their grammatical relationships. She links this information to her experience. Perhaps she thinks, “Ah, the temperature is going to drop by 5 degrees.” Drawing on her experience, she concludes, “A sweater probably won’t be enough for tonight; I’ll need a jacket.” So, a person uses

a clear measurement (temperature), combines it with their experience, and deduces the significance of the change.

```
ex:obs001 a sofa:Observation ;
  sofa:observedProperty ex:airTemperature ;
  sofa:hasFeatureOfInterest ex:station_Knipping ;
  sofa:madeBySensor ex:thermometer_K1 ;
  sofa:resultTime "2026-05-14T12:00:00+09:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  sofa:hasSimpleResult "21.1"^^xsd:decimal ;
  qudt:unit unit:DEG_C .

ex:obs002 a sofa:Observation ;
  sofa:observedProperty ex:airTemperature ;
  sofa:hasFeatureOfInterest ex:station_Knipping ;
  sofa:madeBySensor ex:thermometer_K1 ;
  sofa:resultTime „2026-05-14T18:00:00+09:00"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  sofa:hasSimpleResult „16.1"^^xsd:decimal ;
  qudt:unit unit:DEG_C .
```

Figure 8: A computer processes temperature measurements from the “Knipping” monitoring station. The individual lines define various pieces of information and link them via websites, as illustrated by the example of “sofa:Observation” in Figure 9.

Figure 8 shows, step by step, how a computer interprets the temperature difference. The first line states that this is an observation. The second line specifies that the observed variable is the air temperature. The third and fourth lines add that the temperature was measured at the “Knipping” station using the “K1” thermometer. This is followed by the exact timestamps for the noon and evening readings, as well as the measured values of 21.5 and 16.1, each as a decimal number. At the end, the unit, degrees Celsius, is specified. This is how the basic principle works. The key point is that behind each piece of this information lies a clearly defined webpage. This is called a *persistent identifier*, such as the well-known DOI for documents (*digital object identifier*). This allows the machine to recognize the individual elements. To put them into a meaningful context, the webpages are linked, much like we connect the subject, predicate, and object in a sentence. This creates a knowledge network, which is huge and infinitely expandable. For example, the temperature difference could be linked to data for clothing recommendations or to additional information about Erwin Knipping.

Figure 9 shows the website behind the computer instruction “sofa:Observation.” It provides the information that the data to be interpreted is an observation. On the linked website, the machine-readable definition of observation is described in detail and logically linked to other information. So we learn that an observation is a process that estimates or calculates a value and leads to a result. Specifically: every observation has at least one value (sofa:hasResult MIN 1) and can only be measured at a specific point in time (sofa:phenomenonTime EXACTLY 1). These entries also include links to websites and lead to further topics such as “Sensor” and so on and so forth. Only through these clearly defined links can a machine logically connect information and thus gain “understanding”.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/#SOSAObservation`. On the left, there is a vertical sidebar with the text "W3C Recommendation" and a "TABLE OF CONTENTS" section. The table of contents lists sections from 1. Introduction to 4.4.1 Overview and examples. The main content area is titled "4.3.2.2 sosa:Observation" and contains the following information:

- IRI:** `http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/Observation`
- a OWL Class**
- Observation** - Act of carrying out an (Observation) [Procedure](#) to estimate or calculate a value of a property of a [FeatureOfInterest](#). Links to a [Sensor](#) to describe what made the [observation](#) and how; links to an [ObservableProperty](#) to describe what the result is an estimate of, and to a [FeatureOfInterest](#) to detail what that property was associated with.
- Example**

The activity of estimating the intensity of an Earthquake using the Mercalli intensity scale is an [Observation](#) as is measuring the moment magnitude, i.e., the energy released by said earthquake.
- Restrictions**
 - `sosa:madeBySensor` **EXACTLY 1**
 - `sosa:madeBySensor` **ONLY** `sosa:Sensor`
 - `sosa:usedProcedure` **ONLY** `sosa:Procedure`
 - `sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest` **EXACTLY 1**
 - `sosa:hasFeatureOfInterest` **ONLY** `sosa:FeatureOfInterest`
 - `sosa:observedProperty` **EXACTLY 1**
 - `sosa:observedProperty` **ONLY** `sosa:ObservableProperty`
 - `ssn:wasOriginatedBy` **EXACTLY 1**
 - `ssn:wasOriginatedBy` **ONLY** `ssn:Stimulus`
 - `sosa:phenomenonTime` **EXACTLY 1**
 - `sosa:hasResult` **MIN 1**
 - `sosa:hasResult` **ONLY** `sosa:Result`
 - `sosa:resultTime` **EXACTLY 1**

At the bottom right of the main content area, there are links: "[Hide additional SSN axioms][Back to module overview and examples][Back to top]"

Figure 9: Online specification of the definition observation through persistent identifiers, see also “sosa:Observation” in Fig. 8. See .

For the sake of completeness, it should be noted that the computer instructions are written in RDF, a standard for describing data on the Internet. RDF stands for “*Resource Description Framework*.”

Now we have everything we need to understand how knowledge can be digitally transmitted from data: knowledge building blocks are clearly defined and organized into logical relationships. Statements about an object are grouped together, creating a context that goes beyond the mere presentation of tables such as Knipping’s. Complex knowledge networks enable simultaneous access to all tables distributed across many OAG issues, as well as to additional tables, records, logging regulations, and books. In our example, this bundling is evident in the instruction “`ex:obs001`,” right at the beginning of Fig. 3. It means that all subsequent information is to be summarized in the object “`obs001`.” This object, in turn, is linked to others, such as “Person Erwin Knipping,” as defined on Wikidata (see Figure 10).

Wikidata, a free and open knowledge database, collects structured data and makes it accessible to both humans and machines. As part of the Wikimedia family, it is operated by the Wikimedia Foundation. In the entry for Knipping - more specifically, item Q11291134 - we learn in several languages that he was a German meteorologist, along with details about his life. This makes it clear who the person is. The website also links to the Wikipedia page about Knipping, which further enriches the context. Incidentally, during our research we noticed that there is no Wikidata entry⁴ for the OAG yet. Anyone

⁴There is already a detailed Wikipedia entry about the OAG (Editor’s note).

wikidata.org/wiki/Q11291134

WIKIDATA Search Wikidata Search

Erwin Knipping (Q11291134)

Item Discussion Read

German meteorologist (1844–1922) edit
 Erwin Rudolf Theobald Knipping

▼ In more languages
 Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	Erwin Knipping	–	
English	Erwin Knipping	German meteorologist (1844–1922)	Erwin Rudolf Theobald Knipping
German	Erwin Knipping	deutscher Meteorologe und Kartograf	Erwin Rudolf Theobald Knipping
French	Erwin Knipping	No description defined	
Bavarian	Erwin Knipping	No description defined	

[All entered languages](#)

Statements

instance of human edit
 ▼ 0 references
 + add reference
 + add value

image edit

Figure 10: The screenshot shows a small excerpt from the entry about Knipping in Wikidata. (► <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q11291134>)

who wishes to do so can create or expand this entry at any time. After all, the Semantic Web thrives on volunteer work.

Global institutions now systematically coordinate and standardize. Organizations such as the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) play a central role. Tim Berners-Lee, the inventor of the Web, founded it back in 1994. National organizations also contribute to knowledge organization. In Japan, the Japanese Science and Technology Agency (JST) leads the way in data standardization and interoperability. Europe, on the other hand, operates in a less centralized manner: The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) sets general standards, CENELEC focuses on electrotechnical standards, and ETSI develops telecommunications and digital standards, Internet protocols, and communication infrastructures. In the research sector, Europe has adopted a coordinated, rule-based approach with common standards and institutional frameworks. Projects such as the European Open Science Cloud aim to make data uniformly accessible and usable across borders. To this end, there are, for example, mandatory guidelines for data processing in research projects. Specifically, the so-called FAIR principles must be applied. FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Japan is taking a somewhat different path, placing greater emphasis on collaboration with industry and adopting a less prescriptive approach. For research projects, for example, the FAIR standards are merely recommended and not mandatory.

Conclusion

Digitizing historical data requires extensive linking of knowledge and context. Only in this way can computers process information and make it useful for various target groups. Knipping's meteorological records demonstrate just how complex this procedure is – and how much potential lies in the collaboration between humans and machines.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the OAG (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Natur- und Völkerkunde Ostasiens) and Maike Röder for her invaluable assistance in accessing the OAG archives and providing historical data. We would also like to express our gratitude to Yvonne Kurz from the German Meteorological Service (Deutscher Wetterdienst) and Ralf Kraack from the Weather Museum Lindenberg (Wettermuseum Lindenberg) for their guidance on the historical context and for providing additional archival reports. We also thank Junichi Fuji from Waseda University Library for his contributions to discussions regarding historical Mining Department observations. Last but not least, we thank Timothy Peter Marcroft for the language review of the English version. This study received no dedicated financial support beyond the authors' affiliations as professors at the Western Norway University of Applied Sciences.

Author Biographies

Dr. Valeria Jana Schwanitz, who holds master degrees in physics and econo-physics and a doctorate in economics, is a professor in Climate Change and Energy Economics at the Western Norwegian University of Applied Sciences. She regularly travels to Japan for personal and professional reasons. She has been a fellow of the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD), a fellow of the Japanese Association of University Women, and a visiting scholar at Kyoto University, Osaka University, Ryukyu University, and the Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology (OIST).

Dr. August Wierling, who holds a master and Ph.D. in physics, is a professor at the Western Norwegian University of Applied Sciences. He conducts research on sustainable energy systems using data-driven, statistical methods. He also regularly travels to Japan for personal and professional reasons. Among other things, he was a fellow of the Japanese Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) and DAAD at Kyoto and Osaka universities and a visiting scholar at Ryukyu University.

Bibliography and References

Amaguchi, H., Olsson, J., Kawamura, A., and Imamura, Y. (2024): Evaluation of climate change impacts on urban flooding using high-resolution rainfall data. *Proceedings of the International Association of Hydrological Sciences*, Vol. 386, 133–140.

Brimblecombe, P. and Hayashi, M. (2018): Pressures from long-term environmental change at the shrines and temples of Nikkō. *Heritage Science*, Vol. 6, p. 27.

Brönnimann, S., Filipiak, J., Chen, S., and Pfister, L. (2024): The weather of 1740, the coldest year in central Europe in 600 years, *Climate of the Past*, 20, 2219–2235.

Central Meteorological Observatory of Japan (1893): Organization of the Meteorological System in Japan. Online: <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/009262018>

Christidis, N., Aono, Y., and Stott, P. A. (2022): Human influence increases the likelihood of extremely early cherry tree flowering in Kyoto. *Environmental Research Letters*, Vol. 17, 054051.

Fujimoto, M. and Nishiura, H. (2022): Baseline scenarios of heat-related ambulance transports under climate change in Tokyo, Japan. *PeerJ*, Vol. 10, e13838.

Hansa (1922): *Hansa –International Maritime Journal*, Vol. 59, p. 1409.

Hibino, G. and Masui, T. (2024): Development of AIM (Asia–Pacific Integrated Model) and its contribution to policy-making for the realization of decarbonized societies in Asia. *Sustainability Science*, Vol. 19, pp. 223–239.

Higashino, M. and Stefan, H. G. (2020): Hydro-climatic Change in Japan (1906–2005): Impacts of Global Warming and Urbanization. *Air, Soil and Water Research*, 7(1).

- Instructions (1858): *Instructions for Observers at Meteorological Stations in the Prussian State*, E.S. Mittler Publishing House, Berlin.
- Instructions (1879): Royal Prussian Meteorological Institute, *Instructions for Completing the New Observation Form*, Schade, Berlin.
- Ishizaki, N. N., Shiogama, H., Hanasaki, N., and Takahashi, K. (2022): Development of CMIP6-based climate scenarios for Japan using statistical methods and their applicability to heat-related impact studies. *Earth and Space Science*, Vol. 9, e2022EA002451.
- Kamei, M., Hanaki, K., and Kurisu, K. (2016): Tokyo's long-term socioeconomic pathways: Towards a sustainable future. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, Vol. 27, pp. 73–82.
- Knipping, E. (1873a): *OAG Communications*, Vol. I (1873–1876), No. 1, p. 3. Knipping, E. (1873b): *OAG Communications*, Vol. I (1873–1876), No. 3, pp. 7–9.
- Knipping, E. (1876): *OAG Communications*, Volume II (1876–1880), Appendix.
- Knipping, E. (1881): *Journal of the Austrian Meteorological Society*, Vol. 16, p. 221.
- Knipping, E. (1884): Weather telegraphy in Japan. *OAG-Mitteilungen*, Vol. IV (1884–1888), No. 31, pp. 11–17.
- Koch, M. and Puster, A. (2014): *E. Knipping, In Japanese Service: Two Decades of a Prussian Meteorologist in the First Half of the Meiji Era (1868–1912)*, Cass Verlag.
- Otake, T. (2023): Fall Is the New Summer: Warming Threatens Japan's Cultural Calendar. *Japan Times*, Nov. 19, 2023.
- Tougou, D., Musolin, D. L., and Fujisaki, K. (2009): Some like it hot! Rapid climate change promotes changes in distribution ranges of *Nezara viridula* and *Nezara antennata* in Japan. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata*, Vol. 130, pp. 249–258. World Meteorological Organization (2024). *State of the Global Climate 2024* (WMO-No. 1368).
- Yoshio, M. and Ishii, M. (2001): Relationship between cold hardiness and northward invasion in the great mormon butterfly, *Papilio memnon* L. (Lepidoptera: Papilionidae) in Japan. *Applied Entomology and Zoology*, Vol. 36, pp. 329–335.
- Zaiki, M. and Mikami, T. (2013): Climate Variations in Tokyo since the Edo Period. *Journal of Geography (Chigaku Zasshi)*, Vol. 122, No. 6, pp. 1010–1019.